

Deliverable 1.6:	Demonstrator
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Dissemination Level:	PU
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Work Package:	WP1: IDMP-related standards and terminologies
Lead partner for this deliverable:	NICTIZ
Partner(s) contributing:	CEN, HL7, WHO-UMC, ISO, GS1 *
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London, UK

Business Lawyer

Diabetic type 1

Humalog Mix50

Helen

38 years old

International Patient Summary

UK
Helen
38 years old

Prescribed medication

Humalog 50 MixDaily
Global PhPID: 0x073AF2E...
Strength: 50,00 units per ml
Dose form: KwikPen, 3ml
MPID: 13...
PCID: 138...

Past medication

Global PhPID: 0xE857DA811B4A6F3BD57810C45D2EA1ED

Pharmacy Information System

Global PhPID: 0xE857DA811B4A6F3BD57810C45D2EA1ED

Resources: AdministrableProductDefinition
MedicinalProductDefinition

MPD Product Look-up

NL MPD (UFIS)

Global PhPID: 0xE857DA811B4A6F3BD57810C45D2EA1ED

Search: [mpd.fhir.server]/AdministrableProductDefinition? identifier=https://www.who-umc.org/phpid[[PhPID]]
&_include=AdministrableProductDefinition:form-of

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Global PhPID: 0xE857DA811B4A6F3BD57810C45D2EA1ED

Pharmacy Information System MPD Product Retrieval

Global PhPID: 0xE857DA811B4A6F3BD57810C45D2EA1ED

1 **640921** MONURIL Granulaat 3000mg/8g in sachet
0xE857DA811B4A6F3BD57810C45D2EA1ED

2 **2940035** FOSFOMYCINE Focus granulaat 3000mg in sachet
0xE857DA811B4A6F3BD57810C45D2EA1ED

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+ [ ] subject
+ [ ] administrableDoseForm
+ [ ] unitOfPresentation
+ [ ] ingredient
+ [ ] routeOfAdministration
+ {} request
  
```

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Package Leaflet

International Patient Summary App

Search

Package Leaflet - Language: English 🇬🇧

AdministrableProductDefinition
MedicinalProductDefinition
List (for Products)

Electronic Product Information (ePI)

UN COM